

Synthesis Characterization of pd (II) and Hg(II) Complexes with Thymine Dithiocarbamate and Phosphines

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Abstract

This research includes synthesis and characterization of some Homogeneous and Heterogeneous binuclear complexes of Pd(II),Hg(II) with mixed ligands of dithiocarbamate derived from Thymine and tertiary phosphines. The formed complexes have the general formula of $[M_2 (T-DTC)_2 (Phosphine)_n]$ Thymine bis(dithiocarbamate) = (T-DTC) M = Pd(II),Hg(II) n=2 or 4 mole. The synthesized complexes were identified using the micro elemental analysis (C.H.N.S), electrical molar conductivity, spectra methods (IR and 1H , ^{31}P -NMR). Antibacterial activity of ligands and complexes was evaluated with two types of bacteria Staphylococcus aureus (gram positive) and Escherichia coli (gram negative). According to the results obtained from the physical and spectral measurements, palladium (II) complexes have a square planer shape, and mercury (II) complexes have a tetrahedral arrangement.

Keywords: Dithiocarbamate, tertiary Phosphine, Thymine bis(dithiocarbamate)

1. Introduction

Dithiocarbamates are S, N containing ligand, which display a rich and varied coordination chemistry with a wide range of transition and main group metal complexes ^[1]. The study of complexes containing sulfur as donor atoms has become an important subject in the field of coordination chemistry ^[2]. Dithiocarbamate compounds are organic compounds ($R \bar{R}NCSS$), where R, \bar{R} are

homogeneous or heterogeneous aliphatic or aromatic organic compounds which are stable with metal ions at high oxidation states due to the strength of the unique bond C-S. It has the electronic system S-C-S ^[3], and it is in a state of resonance, Where the flowing of additional electrons takes place from nitrogen to carbon from π orbitals ^[4] as in the following diagram

:

Due to the significant importance of thiocarbamate derivatives which can be used as potent medicine against cancer and drugs [5]. In agriculture, industry, and biology, also they are used as antimicrobial and immunological regulatory materials [6,7]. And they are used as an intermediate in some reactions. Among the important reactions of dithiocarbamate is the oxidation to thiram disulfide compounds [8]. Using oxidizing agents such as $K_3 [Fe (CN)_6]$, I_2 and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), these types of ligands contain the active group S-S [9].

Such active group might react with metals through the cleavage or without cleavage of S-S bond. Phosphine and diphosphine are important ligands in transition-metal catalyzed reactions, and the electronic and steric effects of the phosphine have pronounced influence on the organic transformation that takes at the transition metal center [10,11].

While the Bis (diphenylphosphino) ethane and the Bis (diphenylphosphino) propane (dppp) behave as bidentate chelate [12], or behave as bridge ligands between two metal atoms [13,14], the complexes of phosphine with palladium used as assistant agent cyclic or heterocyclic by increase stability of

medial compound [15]. In the present work, we report the synthesis and characterization of some new complexes obtained by the reaction of Pd(II), Hg(II) salts with mixed ligands of dithiocarbamate and a tertiary phosphine.

2. Experimental

IR-spectra were recorded on the (FTIR- 600 Spectrophotometer) in the (350-4000) cm-1 range using KBr discs. Micro elemental analysis (C.H.N) conducted by using (Euro EA 3000). Molar Conductivities for complexes were measured at 10-3 M solution in DMSO at 25° C using (Cond 7110). Melting points were obtained using (Electro thermal 9300). The 1H - ^{31}P -NMR spectra were performed (solvent DMSO-d₆) on (Bruker 400MHz), at the University of Sinop, Turkey.

2.1 Starting materials

All chemicals and phosphine ligands were commercial products and were used as supplied.

2.2 Synthesis of ligand

Thymine bis(dithiocarbamate) (T-DTC) was prepared by a previously described method [16].

Table 1: chemical formula (CHNS) analysis and some physical properties of the T-DTC ligand

Chemical formula	Color	Melting point/°C	Micro elemental analysis calculate (found)			
			S%	N%	H%	C%
$C_7H_4N_2Na_2O_2S_4$ 322	Light orange	358-359	46.38 (46.24)	10.22 (10.16)	1.62 (1.50)	30.25 (30.32)

2.3 Synthesis of Dithiocarbamate complexes with phosphine

- Synthesis of $[Pd_2(T-DTC)_2(dppe)_2]$

This complex was synthesized by the following procedure: A solution of $Na_2[PdCl_4]$ (0.018g, 0.000062mol) in distilled water (5ml) was added to a solution of Na_2T-DTC (0.021g, 0.000062mol) in distilled water (5 ml), the

mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 hour). The colour of the solution was changed from colorless to dark brown then a solution of dppe (0.025g, 0.000062mol) in 5ml of acetone was added. The mixture was left stirring for half an hour, a light brown precipitate was formed, and it was filtered off and washed with a small amount of distilled water (3 times) and dried in an oven at 50 °C.

The rest of the complexes listed in (Table 2) were synthesized in the same way as mentioned above using a proper number of moles of the metal salts and ligands.

3. Results And Discussion

Physical and spectral techniques were used for the identification of synthesized complexes. The solid prepared complexes are soluble in most common

solvents such as DMSO, DMF, THF. The molar conductivity values of all complexes in DMSO solvent of 10⁻³ M at 25° C (Table 2) indicate that complexes are non-electrolyte. This is consistent with the stoichiometry assumed for the complexes [M (T-DTC)₂(Phosphine)_n]. The micro elemental analysis measurements for all complexes gave approximated values when are compared with theoretical values,(Table2) includes some physical properties and (C.H.N.S) results for the synthesized complexes.

Table 2: Some physical properties, analytical, conductance data and yield % of the complexes

No	Complexes	Color	M.P/ °C	yield%	Molar cond./ mole ⁻¹ , cm ⁻¹ hom	Micro elemental analysis calculated (found)			
						C%	H%	N%	S%
1.	[pd ₂ (T-DTC) ₂ (dppm) ₂]	Light orange	168-170	72	0.06
2.	[pd ₂ (T-DTC) ₂ (pph ₃) ₄]	orange	240-242	76	0.13	56.92 (55.74)	3.78 (3.44)	3.09 (2.91)	14.13 (13.94)
3.	[pd ₂ (T-DTC) ₂ (dppe) ₂]	Light orange	202-203	67	0.74	50.74 (50.63)	3.61 (3.53)	3.59 (3.40)	16.42 (16.20)
4.	[pd ₂ (T-DTC) ₂ (dppp) ₂]	brouwn	221-223	65	1.22
5.	[Hg ₂ (T-DTC) ₂ (dppm) ₂]	white	210 -211	79	0.36	44.62 (44.51)	3.04 (2.95)	3.25 (3.11)	14.89 (14.72)
6.	[Hg ₂ (T-DTC) ₂ (pph ₃) ₄]	Gray	170 -171	77	0.07
7.	[Hg ₂ (T-DTC) ₂ (dppe) ₂]	Light gray	200-202	63	0.12
8.	[Hg ₂ (T-DTC) ₂ (dppp) ₂]	Dark gray	284-286	64	0.36	45.92 (45.68)	3.40 (3.33)	3.15 (2.98)	14.42 (14.28)

The prominent infrared spectral data of prepared ligand and its complexes are given in (Table 3).

The IR spectra of the complexes were compared with those of the free ligand in order to determine the coordination sites that may be involved in bonding.

In T-DTC, the infrared bands observed at 1689 cm⁻¹, 1438 cm⁻¹, (1130) and (954) cm⁻¹ have been assigned to ν C=O, ν (C-N), ν (C=S) and(C-S) respectively [16]. In IR spectra of all complexes , the C=O stretching vibration are shifted to higher values 1653-1691cm⁻¹, suggesting that the carbonyl group

is not involved in bonding in coordination with central metal ion ^[17].

Also, the complexes spectra showed bands at 1435-1487 cm^{-1} which is assigned to (C-N) group and those values, indicating that (C-N)group is not coordinated ^[18].

A noticeable shift to lower frequencies for bands of (C-S) (891-1001) cm^{-1} , and (1101-1188) cm^{-1} in the complexes were observed .

The ν (C-S) frequencies can be used for distinguishing between the mono and bidentate

binding of dithiocarbamate ligand with the metal ion , the presence of two bands in spectra of the complexes refer to ν (C-S) bonds in spectra of the complexes refer to monodentate coordination of dithiocarbamate ligand with the metal ion ^[19]. The new bands in the region (692-700) cm^{-1} and (1429-1438) cm^{-1} were assigned to ν (P-C) and ν (P-Ph) respectively indicating that phosphine ligands are coordinated with metal center ^[13].

Table 3: IR data of synthesized complexes and ligands (cm^{-1})

Complexes	ν (C-H) Alph. Ar.	ν (C=C)	ν (C=O)	ν (C-N)	ν (C=S) ν (C-S)	ν (P-Ph)	ν (C-Ph)
T-DTC	2951	1595	1689	1438	1130 954
[$\text{Pd}_2(\text{T-DTC})_2(\text{dppm})_2$]	2976 3047	1604	1681	1479	1112 934	1433	696
[$\text{Pd}_2(\text{T-DTC})_2(\text{pph}_3)_4$]	2976 3053	1637	1676	1475	1095 997	1433	694
[$\text{Pd}_2(\text{T-DTC})_2(\text{dppe})_2$]	2970 3064	1620	1685	1475	1118 995	1434	700
[$\text{Pd}_2(\text{T-DTC})_2(\text{dppp})_2$]	2999 3053	1614	1681	1483	1076 1018	1438	692
[$\text{Hg}_2(\text{T-DTC})_2(\text{dppm})_2$]	2982 3059	1581	1691	1477	1138 918	1433	698
[$\text{Hg}_2(\text{T-DTC})_2(\text{pph}_3)_4$]	2964 3036	1614	1691	1477	1091 1001	1429	692
[$\text{Hg}_2(\text{T-DTC})_2(\text{dppe})_2$]	2947 3064	1604	1670	1479	1010 918	1433	698
[$\text{Hg}_2(\text{T-DTC})_2(\text{dppp})_2$]	2922 3070	1624	1653	1487	1026 891	1433	692

3.1 NMR Results

- ¹³C-NMR spectrum of T-DTC

The NMR spectrum of the ¹³C-NMR ligand ($\text{Na}_2\text{T-DTC}$), measured in practice in the deuterium-compensated DMSO solvent, showed seven single signals indicating the presence of seven carbon atoms in the ligand, which corresponds to the number of carbon atoms present in the ligand, measured in practice. The measured spectrum

effectively indicates that the chemical displacement signal $\delta^{13}\text{C} = (12.66)$ ppm returns to the methyl group (CH_3). The spectrum also showed two mono signals at chemical displacement $\delta^{13}\text{C} = (166.81, 157.25)$ ppm due to carbon atoms (C = O). In addition to the appearance of a single signal $\delta^{13}\text{C} = (42.07)$ ppm, which returns to the carbon atoms of the solvent as in Figure (1)

Figure 1: ¹³C NMR spectrum of (Na₂T-DTC)

The NMR spectrum of the complex [Hg₂ (T-DTC)₂ (dppe)₂] shown in Fig. 2 showed a multiple signal in the rings δH = (7.49 - 7.90) ppm and with an integrality corresponding to 40 protons. Eight protonic aromatic protons, located in the ligand dppe, showed the spectrum as a single signal at the site δH = (7.26) ppm due to the protons of the (2C-H group) in the ligand T-DTC. The spectrum

showed a single signal at chemical displacement δH=(1.37)ppm, whose integration indicates that they correspond to six protons to Protons Group (2CH₃) in Ekand T-DTC, and signal mono when chemical displacement δH = (2.51 ppm) as indicating unilateral reference to the protons solvent that these values indicate the presence of Ekanda dppe with Ekanda T-DTC.

Figure 2: ¹H-NMR spectrum of the complex [Pd₂(T-DTC)₂(dppe)₂]

The ³¹P-NMR data for Some prepared complexes using DMSO-d₆ as a Solvent are given in (Table 4), and figures (3) show the spectra for some of them. [20,21].

Figure 3: NMR spectrum of ^{31}P -NMR of complex $[\text{Hg}_2(\text{T-DTC})_2(\text{dppp})_2]$

Table 4: ^{31}P -NMR data δ ^{31}P ppm of some prepared complexes are all singlet

No.	Complex	δ_p
1.	$[\text{Hg}_2(\text{T-DTC})_2(\text{dppp})_2]$	24.08
2.	$[\text{Hg}_2(\text{T-DTC})_2(\text{dppe})_2]$	30.19
3.	$[\text{Pd}_2(\text{T-DTC})_2(\text{pph}_3)_4]$	25.60
4.	$[\text{Pd}_2(\text{T-DTC})_2(\text{dppm})_2]$	48.52

Table 5: ^1H -NMR spectral data for some complexes

No.	Complex
5.	^1H -NMR(DMSO- d_6): δ 7.30-7.54(40H,Phos) for 8 cycle aromatic, δ 3.01(4H,CH ₂ , ligand dppm), δ 2.09(6H,2CH ₃ ,ligand phos), 7.77(2H,2CH,ligand phos) dppm
6.	^1H -NMR(DMSO- d_6): δ 7.31-7.67(60H,Phos) for 12 cycle aromatic, δ 1.37(6H,2CH ₃ ,ligand phos), δ 3.01(4H,CH ₂ ,ligandT-DTC)ppm., 7.26(2H,2CH,ligand phos) PPh ₃

3.2 Anti-bacterial activity

The synthesized dithiocarbamate ligand and its complexes were tested against two types of bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* (gram positive) and *Escherichia coli* (gram negative). DMSO was used as solvent and as a control. The concentration of the compound in this solvent were (1×10^{-3}) , (1×10^{-2}) and (1×10^{-1}) mg/ml. The disc sensitivity test method was used, the incubation was held for 24

hours at 37 °C. The measured inhibition zones against amounts of growth of two types of bacteria are summarized in (Table5) that displays the effect of synthesized compounds on bacterial strains. The results revealed that some of the metal complexes have nearly the same activity or to be more active in comparison with the ligands and that means upon complexation may lead to slight increase of inhibition against bacteria. Antibiotics have been used are: Ampicillin, Amoxicillin.

Table 5: Results of antibacterial study of complexes and prepared ligands

No.	Complexes	Con c.mg /ml	<i>staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
1.	T-DTC	1 x 10 ⁻³	+	-
		1 x 10 ⁻²	+	+
		1 x 10 ⁻¹	+++	++
2.	[Pd ₂ (T-DTC) ₂ (dppm) ₂]	1 x 10 ⁻³	-	+
		1 x 10 ⁻²	-	+
		1 x 10 ⁻¹	+	+++
3.	[Pd ₂ (T-DTC) ₂ (dppp) ₂]	1 x 10 ⁻³	-	+
		1 x 10 ⁻²	+	++
		1 x 10 ⁻¹	++	+++
4.	[Pd ₂ (T-DTC) ₂ (pph ₃) ₄]	1 x 10 ⁻³	-	-
		1 x 10 ⁻²	+	+
		1 x 10 ⁻¹	+	++
5.	[Pd ₂ (T-DTC) ₂ (dppe) ₂]	1 x 10 ⁻³	-	-
		1 x 10 ⁻²	-	+
		1 x 10 ⁻¹	-	++
6.	[Hg ₂ (T-DTC) ₂ (dppm) ₂]	1 x 10 ⁻³	-	-
		1 x 10 ⁻²	-	+
		1 x 10 ⁻¹	-	+
7.	[Hg ₂ (T-DTC) ₂ (dppp) ₂]	1 x 10 ⁻³	+	-
		1 x 10 ⁻²	++	+
		1 x 10 ⁻¹	+++	++
8.	[Hg ₂ (T-DTC) ₂ (pph ₃) ₄]	1 x 10 ⁻³	+	-
		1 x 10 ⁻²	+	+
		1 x 10 ⁻¹	++	++
9.	[Hg ₂ (T-DTC) ₂ (dppe) ₂]	1 x 10 ⁻³	+	-
		1 x 10 ⁻²	++	+
		1 x 10 ⁻¹	++	++

(-) = There is no inhibition
 (+) =Inhibition of 5 - 15 mm diameter
 (++) =Inhibition of 2 - 15 mm diameter
 (+++) =Inhibition of 25 to 35 mm diameter

Figure (4): The inhibitory activity of the complex [Hg₂(T-DTC)₂(dppe)₂] and [Pd₂(T-DTC)₂(dppm)₂] against bacteria *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

4. Conclusions

Based on analytical and spectral results, the T-DTC acts as a monodentate ligand which is bonded with the metal ions through a single sulfur atom while phosphine ligands is coordinated with the metal ions in a different modes ,pPh₃ was coordinated as a monodentate ligand, dppm coordinate through one

phosphine atom behaved and dppe and dppp behaved as a bidentate ligands.

The geometrical structures for synthesized complexes can be proposed as follows:

*Square planner structure for palladium complexes

$[\text{Pd}_2(\text{T-DTC})_2(\text{dppe})_2]$

$[\text{Pd}_2(\text{T-DTC})_2(\text{dppm})_2]$

$[\text{Pd}_2(\text{T-DTC})_2(\text{PPh}_3)_4]$

$$[\text{Pd}_2(\text{T-DTC})_2(\text{dppp})_2]$$

***Tetrahedral geometry for mercury complexes**

$$[\text{Hg}_2(\text{T-DTC})_2(\text{dppm})_2]$$

$$[\text{Hg}_2(\text{T-DTC})_2(\text{PPh}_3)_4]$$

[Hg₂(T-DTC)₂(dppp)₂]

5. References

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